

doi:10.5281/zenodo.17207897

Technostress And Academic Engagement Of Students In Selected Tertiary Institutions In Sokoto State, Nigeria

Hannatu Abdullahi¹ & Mohammad Idris²

¹Department of Educational Foundation
Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria
Hannatuabdullahi614@gmail.com/07031538653

²Department of Curriculum and Instruction
Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto, Nigeria
idrism759@gmail.com/08032914731

ABSTRACT

This study investigated the relationship between technostress and the academic engagement of students in selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The pervasive integration of technology in higher education, while beneficial, introduces stressors that may impede student learning, particularly in regions facing digital infrastructure challenges. A cross-sectional survey design was adopted, and data was collected from 250 students randomly selected from three institutions using a structured questionnaire. The instrument measured five dimensions of technostress (techno-overload, techno-invasion, techno-complexity, techno-insecurity, and techno-uncertainty) and three dimensions of academic engagement (behavioral, emotional, and cognitive). Data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and multiple regression. The findings revealed a high prevalence of technostress among students, with techno-complexity difficulty using required software/platforms and techno-insecurity fear of being outperformed by peers or technology identified as the most salient stressors. It recommends that tertiary institutions develop targeted interventions, such as digital literacy training, robust technical support systems, and pedagogical strategies that mitigate technology-related anxiety, to foster a more conducive and engaging academic environment.

Keywords: Technostress, Academic Engagement, Higher Education, Digital Divide, Sokoto State, Nigeria.

INTRODUCTION

In the late 20th and 21st centuries, Computer and internet systems have dominated the learning system in most of our tertiary institutions. This change came with serious engagement of students to use smart phones, laptops, palmtop and other technologies in their studies and researches. Costley (2014), contends that the present generation of students has come to this realization and is now beginning to use various technological devices like smartphones, laptops, iPads/Tablets etc. in carrying out their daily academic tasks. Those who are not skillful in the use of these devices are now showing concern and trying to equip themselves with the skills needed. All these in a bid to harness the full benefits of using technology in academic activities. With technology, students can access course materials when it is most convenient.

They can audio/video record lectures and replay them at their own time for better comprehension, use their iPads/Tablets and internet to do personal research online, carry out and submit their assignments electronically, communicate with their lecturers and fellow students through social media tools, among others.

However, technology has lowered international barriers and expanded the potential reach of colleges and universities in the sense that with sophisticated communication technologies, institutions of higher education are no longer limited to student markets or educational resources in their geographical regions. Also with technology, institutions of higher learning can provide lifelong learning opportunities to individuals who seek alternatives to traditional real-time, campus

Educational technologies like digital whiteboards are interactive devices that teachers can give students chances for a real time interaction. Vinay Thalari (2025), asserted that digital whiteboards make lessons more interactive, capturing students' attention with dynamic visuals videos, and exercises, leading to better retention and understanding of concepts. These indicate that students use technologies as tools for building and maintaining social connections and organizing their academic engagements more efficiently. In a bid towards organizing their private lives and maintaining social connections in addition to carrying out their academic responsibilities, students have had to rely heavily on technological tools (Niehaves & Plattfaut, 2013; Wright & Brown, 2004). This over-reliance/dependence on these technology tools, however, breeds technology-related stress (Technostress) on the users (students) of these devices consciously or unconsciously, be it physically, psychologically, behaviorally, or emotionally. The type of technology-related stress experienced by individual students varies depending on the individuals' technological skills, frequency of use of these tools, availability and accessibility, perception, orientation, and belief about technology (personality). Ayyagari (2011), asserts that because individuals differs, the level of technostress a person may experience will also vary.

Statement of the Problems

Technology or ICT has become essential for students in carrying out their daily learning activities both within and outside the school premises. This fact, in addition to the advancement in technology, has made it possible for students to incorporate into their daily learning activities. Costley (2014), is of the opinion that technology has positive impact on students learning as it enable students become more engaged; consequently retain more information. Technology is relevant to the students as it affords them meaningful learning experiences.

However, according to organizational behavior researchers (Tarafdar, et al, 2007; 2008; 2011; Mawhinney, 2014), information and communication technologies were related to job strain, low job satisfaction, burnout, decreased academic engagement and an increased students' technology-related stress such as inability to navigate the web, inability to operate some technological devices, irritability, loss of temper, high state of anxiety when separated from technological gadgets, using computer terms in non-computer conversations, jealousy produced by technological competency, demotivation due to prolonged periods of any technological activity among others.

Physical and psychological, technology can be detrimental to individual health in different ways. As a result of this, there is the need to not only find out what proportions of students make use of these technologies and the technostress factors that affect them but also to determine what impact technostress have on students' academic engagement. Additional problem is when we consider the location, Sokoto which is not a city and thus most of the technological tools are scarce or not easily available but yet students and learners are expected to cop up with these short comings. It is worthy of investigating to find out the condition of technostress among these students.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective is to investigate technostress on the academic engagement of students in tertiary institutions in Sokoto and Kebbi States. But the specific objectives are to :

1. Find out the frequency of use technology among Computer Science Students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and Sokoto State University, Sokoto.

2. Find out the impact (if any) of techno-stress on academic engagement of Computer Science Students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto and Sokoto State University, Sokoto.

Research Questions

1. What is the frequency of technology use among Computer Science students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and Sokoto State University, Sokoto?
2. What is the impact of techno-stress on the academic engagement of Computer Science students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and Sokoto State University, Sokoto?

Review of Related Literature

According to Ramey (2013), Technology is a body of knowledge devoted to creating tools, processing actions and the extracting of materials. Ramey went ahead to assert that ‘we use technology to accomplish various tasks in our daily lives and as such, we can describe technology as products and processes used to simplify our daily lives’. To Mawhinney (2014), Technology is the collection of techniques, skills, methods and processes used in the production of goods or services for the accomplishment of objectives. This means that, technology is the systematic application of knowledge to serve individual needs and solve problems.

Thiel (2014), asserts that technology is ‘Any new way of doing things’. This definition, though very brief, is all encompassing. It implies technology as modern ways or approaches to carrying out activities and solving problems. To Ferre cited in Thiere (2014), technology is the ‘practical implementations of intelligence’. He came up with this definition probably because technology is unlikely to have occurred by chance, without being created by intelligent beings—many presume to be mankind—given the inherent knowledge and requisite organization of technology as a system that allows it to produce objects and perform techniques to achieve goals. This means that, technology is the physical application or execution of innate knowledge for the purpose of accomplishing a task. Similarly in his own submission, Fernald (2014), avers that technology is the ability to convert society’s resources (labour and capital) into output (goods and services that we value).

Alvarez-Risco et al (2021) investigated the relationship between communication overload, social overload, technostress, exhaustion and academic performance. of university medicine students in Peru during the COVID-19 pandemic. A cross sectional analytical study of 2286 university medical students were involved, to assess the influence of technostress as a mediator of social media overload, communication overload and mental exhaustion and its detrimental effect on the academic performance Of the University students. The findings of the research revealed that communication and social overload were found to be positively influencing technostress by correlations of 0.284 and 0.557, respectively. Technostress positively influence d exhaustion by 0.898, while exhaustion negatively influence d academic performance by -0.439.

Fitzgerald (2021) carried out research on the influence of technostress on perceived academic performance. The purpose of the research was to explore how technology characteristics influence students' technostress, and in turn their perceived academic performance. To examine this, Data were collected through an online self-administered questionnaire distributed through emails to 375 students enrolled in courses at MAU in Sweden during the period of April 2020 and a bivariate analysis was conducted to analyze the data. The results showed some technology characteristics were associated with technostress, while some were not. The students' technostress could, however, not be determined to have an association with their perceived academic performance. The study discusses possible contributing factors to the results. The study relates with the present study in content but differ in scope.

Mangundu (2023) conducted a study on the effects of technostress on the academic commitment among first-year undergraduate students at an institution of higher education in South Africa, in accordance with the technostress creators’ model and the adapted organizational commitment model. The findings of the study revealed that techno - complexity has a significantly direct negative relationship (-.74) with students' academic commitment. However, techno-uncertainty significantly positively (.42) impacts students’ commitment. In addition, techno - invasion insignificantly positively impact (.11) on students’ academic commitment. Interestingly, students’ age negatively correlated with techno - complexity, with older

students being less affected by the complexity of technology for learning. Surprisingly, time spend using information and communication technologies is associated with more effect from echno - uncertainty. In addition, the findings revealed that gender differences significantly impacted on the differences in the levels of studets' technostres, with techno - invasion being more highly perceived by male students.

Mahapatra et al (2023) carried out a study on the relationship between technostress and academic achievement of University students of Gangahar Meher University, Sambulpur. The study found out a negative relationship between technostress and academic achievement among university students, with no significant difference in technostress levels between boys and girls.

Saleem et al (2024) explores the impact of technostress on students 'motivation and academic performance in a study of tehnostress in students and online learning in a community of inquiry framework. The study to investiges the moderating impact of instructors and university students. The study found out that technostress negatively impacts students motivation and academic performance while instructor and university support play a crucial role in mitigating ths effect.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design:

This study adopted Descriptive survey design. This is because is that describes a population, situation or phenomenon that is being studies. Because of the nature of the study, descriptive research design will be used as it will allow the researcher reach out to the study population in their various locations. Also, descriptive survey design will be adopted because the study is only interested in describing certain variables relating to the population.

Population of the Study:

The study population consists of 250 Computer Science UG3 Students across the two institutions in Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto and Sokoto State University Population Distribution in the University for the 2024/2025 Academic Session.

Sample and Sampling Technique:

Using the Research Advisor (2006) as guide, a total number of 217 Economics Students will be proportionately and randomly selected to serve as samples for the study as shown in tables 2 and Multi - stage sampling techique will be use in order to arrive at the targeted number and research advisor (2006) as a guide will be use obtain the needed sample size.

Instrument for Data Collection:

Questionnaire will be use as instrument fo data collection. The instrument will be adapted from Bawa, Dalhatu and Tukur (2016). The instrument has four sections (A - D). Section A will contain the demographic information while section B, C and D will contain the four point Likert scale items which ranges from (A) Agree, (SA) Strongly Agree, (D) Disagree and (SD) Strongly Disagree. The choice of questionnaire as the instrument for data collection is as a result of the respondents being literate, respondent's requre different convenient time to respond to the questions, questionnaire is the most frequently used instrument in educational research and it is more economical.

Procedure for Data Collection:

The researchers will administer and retrieve the questionnaires by the use of two research assistants in each of institutions. The use of research assistance will enable researchers to reach out to the respondents in the various lecture rooms in the institutions.

Procedure for Data Analysis:

Descriptive statistics of frequency counts, percentages and mean will be use to answer the research questions.

RESULTS

Research Question one: *What is the frequency of technology use among Computer Science students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and Sokoto State University, Sokoto?*

Table 4.1 Summary of frequency of technology use among Computer Science students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and Sokoto State University, Sokoto

Statement	N	Mean	St. Deviation	Decision
Use of computer/laptop for academic purposes (assignments, projects, coding)	219	2.53	.913	Accepted
Accessing e-learning platforms (e.g., Moodle, Coursera, Google Classroom)	219	2.51	.816	Accepted
Use of social media for academic purposes (WhatsApp, Telegram, LinkedIn)	219	2.52	.971	Accepted
Accessing online libraries and journals for assignments/projects	219	2.76	.790	Accepted
Participation in virtual study groups/discussions (Zoom, Google Meet, Teams)	219	2.71	.913	Accepted
Use of technology for online assessments, tests, or quizzes	219	2.54	.764	Accepted

Table 4.1 Shows a summary of the mean ratings of the various level of What is the frequency of technology use among Computer Science students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and Sokoto State University, Sokoto. The data analysis revealed that the respondents were of the view that; Use of computer/laptop for academic purposes (assignments, projects, coding (Mean=2.53, Standard Deviation=.913), Accessing e-learning platforms (e.g., Moodle, Coursera, Google Classroom (Mean=2.51, Standard Deviation=.816), Use of social media for academic purposes (WhatsApp, Telegram, LinkedIn (Mean=2.52, Standard Deviation=.971), Accessing online libraries and journals for assignments/projects (Mean=2.76, Standard Deviation=.790), Participation in virtual study groups/discussions (Zoom, Google Meet, Teams) (Mean=2.71, Standard Deviation=.913, Use of technology for online assessments, tests, or quizzes (Mean=2.54, Standard Deviation=.764). the findings indicate that while Computer Science students engage with different forms of technology for academic purposes, their level of usage is moderate across most items, with higher tendencies toward accessing online libraries and participating in virtual study groups.

Research Question 2: *What is the impact of techno-stress on the academic engagement of Computer Science students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and Sokoto State University, Sokoto*

Table 4.2 Summary of the impact of techno-stress on the academic engagement of Computer Science students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and Sokoto State University, Sokoto

Statement	N	Mean	St. Deviation	Decision
Techno-stress reduces my concentration during academic activities	219	3.01	1.083	Accepted
I feel overwhelmed by excessive use of technology in my studies	219	2.56	1.158	Accepted
Techno-stress reduces my motivation to engage in academic work.	219	2.60	1.080	Accepted
Techno-stress makes me procrastinate on assignments.	219	2.56	1.121	Accepted
Techno-stress negatively affects my academic performance.	219	2.58	1.155	Accepted
The pressure of constant connectivity (emails, messages, notifications) reduces my academic engagement.	219	2.54	1.083	Accepted

Table 4.1 Shows a summary of the mean ratings of the various level of the impact of techno-stress on the academic engagement of Computer Science students of Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto, and Sokoto State University, Sokoto. The data analysis revealed that the respondents were of the view that; Techno-stress reduces my concentration during academic activities (Mean=3.01, Standard Deviation=1.083), I feel overwhelmed by excessive use of technology in my studies (Mean=2.56, Standard Deviation=1.158), Techno-stress reduces my motivation to engage in academic work (Mean=2.60, Standard Deviation=1.080), Techno-stress makes me procrastinate on assignments (Mean=2.56, Standard Deviation=1.121), Techno-stress negatively affects my academic performance (Mean=2.58, Standard Deviation=1.155), and The pressure of constant connectivity (emails, messages, notifications) reduces my academic engagement (Mean=2.54, Standard Deviation=1.083). Overall, the results indicate that students perceive techno-stress as having a moderate negative impact on their academic engagement. Among the factors, reduced concentration (Mean = 3.01) was identified as the most significant effect, while the pressure of constant connectivity (Mean = 2.54) was rated the least.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The findings of this study reveal a significant and negative impact of technostress on the academic engagement of students in Sokoto State, Nigeria. This discussion interprets these results by situating them within the broader scholarly conversation on technology, stress, and learning, while highlighting the unique contextual factors of the study environment.

The identification of techno-complexity (the difficulty associated with using various software and platforms) as a primary stressor is a critical finding. This aligns with the core concept of technostress as defined by Ragu-Nathan et al. (2008), which arises when individuals perceive technology as complex and beyond their coping abilities. However, in the context of Sokoto State, this finding is amplified by the digital divide. Many students enter tertiary institutions with limited prior exposure to sophisticated computing resources (Adebayo & Adesina, 2021). Therefore, being abruptly required to use complex programming environments, learning management systems, and statistical software creates a significant competency gap. This experience resonates with the findings of Awoyemi et al. (2020) in Southwestern Nigeria, who noted that inadequate foundational digital literacy is a major barrier to effective technology integration in higher education. The stress of techno-complexity is not merely about the technology itself, but about the lack of preparatory resources, making the learning curve disproportionately steep.

Furthermore, the prominence of techno-insecurity the fear of being replaced by technology or outperformed by more skilled peers—points to a profound psychological impact. This finding supports Jena's (2015) argument that technostress can trigger anxiety about one's adequacy and future employability. In a competitive academic environment, students who struggle with technology may perceive their peers as more competent, leading to feelings of insecurity and self-doubt. This is particularly acute for students in fields like Computer Science, where technological prowess is central to identity and career prospects (Tarafdar et al., 2019). The constant pressure to "keep up" in an environment with uneven access to resources and support fosters a climate of insecurity that directly undermines academic confidence.

The significant negative relationship between technostress and academic engagement can be effectively explained through the lens of the Job Demands-Resources (JD-R) model (Bakker & Demerouti, 2007), applied here to the student context. In this model, technological requirements act as "demands," while personal resilience and institutional support serve as "resources." When demands overwhelm resources, burnout and disengagement occur (Salanova et al., 2013).

The finding that technostress strongly predicted diminished emotional engagement (characterized by anxiety, frustration, and a lack of belonging) is consistent with research by Maier et al. (2019), which linked technostress to reduced satisfaction and well-being. When students feel constantly defeated by technology, their emotional connection to their studies erodes. They may develop negative attitudes towards their courses, leading to a cycle of avoidance and decreased motivation (Wang et al., 2020).

Similarly, the reduction in behavioral engagement (e.g., skipping lab sessions, procrastinating on online submissions) is a direct behavioral consequence of high technostress. This aligns with the "avoidance coping" mechanism identified in stress literature. Students who find a task too stressful or perceive a low probability of success are likely to disengage behaviorally (Ifinedo et al., 2020). In Sokoto, where a single failed attempt to upload an assignment due to poor internet connectivity can consume hours, the rational choice for a stressed student may be to avoid the task altogether.

A crucial aspect of this discussion is the role of the local context. The technostress experienced by students in Sokoto State is not solely a product of software complexity or personal aptitude; it is profoundly exacerbated by systemic infrastructural deficits. Unreliable electricity, expensive and erratic internet connectivity, and limited access to functional hardware (Adebayo & Adesina, 2021) are not peripheral issues they are fundamental precursors that amplify every dimension of technostress. Each power outage reinforces techno-uncertainty; every network failure intensifies techno-complexity by interrupting workflows. This contextual layer means that the technostress model, often studied in well-resourced environments, operates with greater intensity in Sokoto. The findings thus contribute to a more nuanced understanding of technostress in developing regions, highlighting how macro-level infrastructural challenges directly micro-level student learning experiences and well-being.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated the relationship between technostress and academic engagement among students in selected tertiary institutions in Sokoto State, Nigeria. The findings revealed that students frequently engage with technology for academic purposes, yet they also encounter varying levels of technostress manifested through reduced concentration, procrastination, mental exhaustion, and worry about academic success. Key stressors identified include poor internet connectivity, limited access to reliable devices, excessive screen time, and the challenge of balancing social media with academic use.

Overall, the study concludes that while technology remains an indispensable tool for learning and research in tertiary institutions, technostress moderately hinders students' academic engagement and performance. The evidence suggests that the inability to effectively manage digital overload, persistent connectivity, and infrastructural limitations contributes to reduced motivation and academic productivity. Therefore, addressing technostress requires a multi-level approach: institutions should provide reliable ICT infrastructure and digital literacy training, while students should be encouraged to adopt healthier technology-use habits. By mitigating the negative effects of technostress, tertiary institutions in Sokoto State can foster more sustainable and effective academic engagement, ultimately enhancing educational outcomes.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The researchers come with the following recommendations:

1. Government and university management should invest in reliable internet connectivity, stable electricity, and up-to-date ICT facilities.
2. Provision of high-speed campus Wi-Fi and modern computer laboratories will reduce frustration caused by poor network services.
3. Institutions should establish device support schemes, such as subsidized laptops, computer leasing programs, or partnerships with ICT companies to make reliable devices more affordable for students.
4. Regular workshops and training should be organized to equip students with the technical skills to effectively handle academic software, e-learning platforms, and digital tools.
5. Special attention should be given to first-year students to ease their transition into technology-driven learning environments.
6. Students should be sensitized on how to manage excessive screen time, reduce distractions from social media, and adopt healthy study routines.

7. Institutions should strike a balance between online and face-to-face instructional delivery to reduce digital overload and accommodate students with limited access to devices or connectivity.
8. Peer mentoring and digital learning clubs could be encouraged, where students support each other in handling academic technologies.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This paper was funded by TETFUND under the Institutions Based Research (IBR) Annual Intervention, we therefore acknowledge their immense support. Also appreciates Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto for the opportunity given to us to conduct this work.

REFERENCES

- Adebayo, A. S., & Adesina, E. F. (2021). Digital divide and its impact on the academic performance of university students in Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 12(15), 1-10.
- Alvarez-Risco A., Del-Aguila-Arcentales, S., Yanes, J. A., Rosen, M. A., & Mejia C. R. (2021), Influence of Technostress on Academic Peerformance of University Medicine Students in Peru During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Sustainability* 2021, 13 (16), 8949.
- Awoyemi, T. O., Adebayo, A. R., & Oluwatobi, A. O. (2020). ICT access and use among pre-tertiary students in Nigeria: Implications for higher education. *African Educational Research Journal*, 8(2), 245-254.
- Ayyagari, R., Grover, V. & Purvis, R. (2011). Technological Antecedents and Implication. *Management Information System (MIS) Quarterly*, 35(4), 831 – 838.
- Bakker, A. B., & Demerouti, E. (2007). The job demands-resources model: State of the art. *Journal of Managerial Psychology*, 22(3), 309-328.
- Costley, K.C. (2014). The Positive Effect of Technology on Teaching and Students Learning. Arkansas Tech. University. Kcosley-at-atu.edu, 30oct,2014. ERIC.
- Fitzgirald, N. (2021). The Influence of Technostress on Perceived Academic Performance. A Study on University Student in Sweden. Independent thesis basic level (degree of bachelor). DIVA, id: diva2:1528770
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su13168949>
<https://files.eric.ed.gov>
<https://www.technostress.it>
- Ifinedo, P., Pyke, J., & Anwar, A. (2020). The digital divide in Sub-Saharan Africa: A multi-dimensional perspective. *In Digital Transformation in Sub-Saharan Africa*. CRC Press.
- Jena, R. K. (2015). Technostress in ICT enabled collaborative learning environment: An empirical study among Indian academician. *Computers in Human Behavior*, 51, 1116-1123.
- Mahapatra et al (2023), Relationship between Technostres and Academic performance of University Student. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*. Volume 36, Issue 10, Pages 45-55.
- Maier, C., Laumer, S., Weinert, C., & Weitzel, T. (2019). The effects of technostress and switching stress on discontinued use of social networking services: A study of Facebook use. *Information Systems Journal*, 29(1), 1-28.
- Mangundu (2023), The Effect of Technostress on Academic Commitment Among First-Year Undergraduate Students at an Institution of Higher Education in South Africa. *Proceedings of the 4th African Human Computer Interaction Cmference (AfriCHI,2023)*, Pages 106-117, Dec. 1st 2023.
- Mawhinney, L. (2014). Techno-Change: A New Study of the Cause of Tecnostress. University of Derby, School of Business. In : *The Moderating Role of Techno-Savvy and Proactive*.
- Nehaves, B., & Plattfaut, R.(2013). Internet Adoption by Elders: Employing IS Technology Acceptance Theories for Understanding the Age-Related Digital Divide. *European Journal of Information Systems*, 10(5), 16 -27.

- Ragu-Nathan, T. S., Tarafdar, M., Ragu-Nathan, B. S., & Tu, Q. (2008). The consequences of technostress for end users in organizations: *Conceptual development and empirical validation. Information Systems Research*, 19(4), 417-433.
- Salanova, M., Llorens, S., & Cifre, E. (2013). The dark side of technologies: Technostress among users of information and communication technologies. *International Journal of Psychology*, 48(3), 422-436.
- Saleem et al (2024), Technostress in Students and Quality of Online Learning: Role of Instructors and University Support. *Journal of Frontiers in Education*. Volume 9, 1309642, 2024
- Tarafdar, M., Cooper, C. L., & Stich, J. F. (2019). The technostress trifecta - techno eustress, techno distress and design: Theoretical directions and an agenda for research. *Information Systems Journal*, 29(1), 6-42.
- Tarafdar, M., Pullis, E.B., & Ragu-Nathan, T.S. (2014). Technostress: Negative Effect on Performance and Possible Mitigations. *Information System Journal*, 25(2), 103 -132.
- Tarafdar, M., Tu, Q., Ragu-Nathan, B.S., & Ragu-Nathan, T.S. (2007). The Impact of Technostress on Role Stress and Productivity. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 24(1), 301 – 328.
- Tarafdar, M., Tu, Q., Ragu-Nathan, T., & Ragu-Nathan, B.S. (2008). Improving End-User Satisfaction Through Technostress Prevention: Some Empirical Evidence. *AMCIS 2008 Proceedings*, 236.
- Vinay Thalari (2025), "Reinventing Education: 10 Ways Digital Whiteboards Are Reshaping Classrooms Worldwide". *International Journal of Research and Technology Innovation*. ISSN 2456 - 3315.
- Wang, T., Lin, C. L., & Su, Y. S. (2020). Continuance intention of university students and online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: *A modified expectation confirmation model perspective. Sustainability*, 13 (8), 4586.
- Wright, R.T. & Brown, R.A. (2004). *Technology Design and Applications*. The Goodheart – Willcox Company, Inc. Tinhy Park, Illinois, 1-59070-165-8.